

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY WITH RISK GROUP CHILDREN

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Abstract

In an environment where societies are integrated and human thought is already electronic, coming to grips with psychological, sociological, as well as pedagogical realities creates deep contradictions between the era and the human factor. Although the measures taken in the direction of minimizing these contradictions and reducing their current effects are effective, it shows that there are different human behaviors and psychologies according to the number of people in the world, and at the same time, the relative similarities of individual actions, as well as individual differences, show themselves as a factor, forcing people to get into smaller details and find ways to solve the problem.

The issue of proper upbringing, which is one of the most prominent problems of all times, remains a rather urgent issue among the works carried out in the direction of improving the current situation of children who are difficult to educate. The main goal of the article presented by us is to give suggestions on the sphere of socio-pedagogical activities carried out in the direction of correct upbringing of children labeled as "belonging to the risk group" and "difficult".

Keywords: Risk group children, "Difficult child", upbringing, children's rights, aggressive children, unruly children, shy children.

Introduction

It is known that people learn by making mistakes and change their ways in the right direction. Humans are born from their mistakes and gain experience. The main thing is that you realize that the mistake you made was a mistake indeed and turn from your path. The biggest problem is when you make a mistake and you don't understand that what you are doing is wrong, you have the right things that you define for yourself and you think that this is how it should be. This misdirection becomes the biggest gap between the individual and the laws of society. Of course, the multifaceted consequences of this gap are not only a general problem of the society, but at the same time they also deal a crushing blow to his family background, educational environment and the foundation of his future life.

First of all, let's pay attention: the word "difficult", "risky", which is the basis of this expression called "difficult upbringing" or "risk group child", is emphasized in this way according to what principles? The existence of that child, either in the family or as a student with the right to education, begins to show itself as a deviation from the norm by the surrounding people. The more parents and other family members are unable to cope with the student in the educational process, the more it becomes an intolerable fact and reality for the members of the teaching staff at the school. Although some educators and school management accepted that child as an "incorrigible learner" and tried to resolve what was happening through physical intervention or psychological support, and at the same time talking with the parent, more experienced school psychologists or teachers looked at life through the eyes of that difficult-to-educate student. They do their best to solve the problem. Sometimes the secret of what seems to be a big problem

lies in the small nuances, and if it is always in front of people's eyes, few people can see that secret.

The risk group begins at the age of 4-5, when children start to differ from their peers, and when they show indifference to their parents' demands, are more inclined to do the opposite of what is said, and start to cause minor damage to surrounding objects. A parent's lack of a bond of upbringing and friendship based on love, strictly fulfilling discipline requirements, imposing physical punishment on his child for mistakes, setting limits on his life and doing all this as if he were applying it to a stranger, at the same time love, if he does it outside the context of caress, the initial germ of great complications begins to germinate. Moral rifts result in larger rifts in the future.

First of all, the parties in the family who can influence the child and develop him as a personality are the mother and the father. Their complementarity and coordination will lead to more joint decisions in the upbringing of their children, which will reduce the possibility of the child falling into a risk group in the future. However, intra-family conflicts create serious gaps in the development of a child and its transition from an individual to a personality, which are filled with useless elements and non-spiritual characteristics in the environment.

Marriage between husband and wife differs from marriage between other people in one important way: it is usually based on a feeling of love. The famous Azerbaijani writer M. S. Ordubadi wrote: "A family is forced to be founded by two people who are new to life and love each other at the same time. They are people who do not resemble each other in terms of personality, image, taste and interest. If there is only one tool they

can refer to for their numbness, to find a common language, it is their love. For this, no matter what they do, they should not allow love to be tarnished, this reference point to be weakened" (Bayramov 2002)

In the family, the words of one of the parents do not agree with the opinion of the other, even the smallest issue becomes a topic of discussion due to financial problems and the conversations take place in front of the child, the absence of one of the parents for various reasons, especially the father's lack of close participation in the upbringing of the child, the mother's responsibility for custody, the child's minor age being exposed to labor exploitation from time to time, the father applying physical violence against the mother and this becoming continuous, the father trying to justify his actions to his child, living with his own truths and dictating those truths as an inevitable law to all members of the family, having alcohol and other addictions, and other similar factors leave irreparable traces in the child's subconscious, so that the shortcomings in education start to trigger the presence of children who are difficult to educate in the future.

If the child has been properly brought up to the age of 6, and certain habits of activity and inhibition have been brought up, then this is no longer scary, no one can have a bad influence on that child. In such cases, they usually say, "We don't control him, but he is developing well, it's probably due to heredity." In truth, this is not from heredity, but from good upbringing, (Makarenko 1937) Even the most powerful earthquakes cannot shake a well-founded building. Any existence with problems in its foundation can be crushed by the slightest vibration.

One of the main principles of family upbringing is the unity of respect and demand for children. Children should be respected at all ages and in all circumstances. Their personality and dignity should not be trampled. It is absolutely unacceptable to make fun of children, insult them, mock them, put them in a ridiculous situation, deceive them, be rude to them, do mental and physical violence, and force them to apologize to others. Strict upbringing accompanied by punishment of the child for the smallest mistakes keeps him in constant fear. Excessively heavy and strict rules lead to disrespect for all rules, so children brought up in such conditions will soon show disrespect for all kinds of laws (Qashamoglu, 2020)

If you don't open the world to the child, if you don't tell him about it, if you don't talk about scientists, writers, artists, cities, museums, spiritual values, he won't have any ideas about the future, so he won't have goals and ideals. A non-ideal person, as the most dangerous creature in the world, will enter such a situation that it will be difficult to define a new road map for him later. It is necessary to arouse impressions about the beauty of the world in the child's mind, to encourage and excite him. The love to live and create must be constantly burning in the child's heart. Just by making him love poetry, by making him like some fairy tale and story, it is possible to create conditions for that child to become a gentle soul and have spiritual wealth in the future. The main thing is to sow the first seed, and others will follow. A parent can keep his child's soul clean

by taking him to museums, theater performances, and associations, and direct him to painting, music, and art in general. A parent who does not determine the child's life path from a young age by gently caressing his wishes may face problems that cannot be overcome in later periods. When we approach the issue from this perspective, the fact that both or one of the parents has a higher education seems to be an important issue, and this is an important nuance in the correct guidance of the child. If a student entering the primary education level with certain deficiencies in the family is not diagnosed at this stage and work is not done to solve the problem, it will not be possible to achieve a positive result, even if the pedagogical staff mobilizes all its levers in the face of the multifaceted actions and behaviors of that student in the upper grades. Just as it is sometimes impossible to treat a disease that is not correctly diagnosed in time, the failure to identify and correct the behavior of children with difficult upbringing in primary school and their neglect leads to the emergence of great complications and realities that are impossible to solve. Since the primary class is the foundation of every secondary general education institution, instilling the standards of knowledge, upbringing and behavior to the student in a normal manner should become the main task of the educators who carry the weight of this stage. Working with students who have no defects in their behavior and do not face difficulties in acquiring scientific knowledge does not require extraordinary skills from the teacher. Dealing with children of the risk group by correcting their wishes, explaining prohibitions and applying them gently, a lot of encouragement, treating the student with parental care will lead to the strengthening of the motive of conscience and an increase in the sense of responsibility, which will lead to the strengthening of the motive of conscience and an increase in the sense of responsibility, which will make him feel loved and embraced while performing some action. It will result in him remembering his teacher and refraining from some bad acts. No student who is treated with love can ever misbehave, with minor exceptions. At a time when everyone needs love, respect, and warmth, leaving some children away from these feelings has a negative impact on their outlook on life.

The Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan recently put forward options as a solution to an issue that is quite important for the educational environment and maintains its relevance, the punishments to be imposed on students who violate the rules of discipline in schools were determined. It is true that although these are not generally the rules presented for at-risk children, they are ultimately considered to be administrative measures to be applied to students who do not conform to discipline and violate the rules in the educational environment according to their level of behavior. These are the following:

- Teacher's view, non-verbal attitude
- Quiet conversation with students
- Warning
- Removal
- Keep in touch with the parent
- Keeping the student at school after school
- Referral to a psychologist

- Yellow warning letter
- Orange warning
- Red alert.

Time will tell what effect the presented will have in the educational environment, but it is possible to find a solution to the problem by going down to the moral, psychological and sociological roots of the issue and spending long-term work in order to solve the unpleasantness and gaps in student behavior.

Ensuring that students of this type study in vocationally oriented classes operating in some schools is also considered a positive step towards solving the problem. There, the lessons conducted by special specialists in computer, cooking, and tailoring directions will ensure that some of the talents accumulated inside the children who are brought up with difficulty will come to light. At the same time, the gathering and education of these types of students in vocationally oriented classes of secondary general educational institutions will create conditions for them to be directed to another vocational field in the future.

Conclusion

Summarizing what has been said, we come to the conclusion that if there are no positive changes in the road maps of children with difficult upbringing, the risk of them committing crimes of various content in the future is high. Although the difficult consequences of the child becoming a criminal will be experienced by that person and the person(s) who were pressured by him, it will not be only those difficult children who will be blamed and punished as criminals. The guilty will be responsible for the persons who made him this way and knowingly or unwittingly caused him to commit a crime at different times, including parents, teachers,

friends, society. While there is time, let's try to shine a light on the future of our future children as much as we can. Let's not become an obstacle in their path to a bright future. The loss of those children will be our loss.

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